

FEATURES OF DIAGNOSTIC RESEARCH METHODS IN SURGICAL TACTICS FOR TREATMENT OF SPLEEN INJURIES

Khakimov M.Sh.
Zhumanazarov A.U.
Ismailova U.A.
Aripov Sh.Sh.

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Relevance. The incidence of spleen injury is 22.3-30% in abdominal organ trauma and ranks second among parenchymatous organ ruptures.

The aim of the study is to determine the most effective methods for diagnosing spleen damage. Modern instrumental research methods allow us to detect even minimal damage to parenchymatous organs, and at present, ultrasound and MSCT are considered the most specific for diagnosing various spleen injuries.

Materials and methods . The results of diagnosis and treatment of 55 patients with closed spleen injury during 2021-2022 in the emergency surgery department of the multidisciplinary clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy are presented for analysis. Of these, 32 (58%) patients were men and the remaining 23 (42%) were women aged 21 to 68 years. Among the victims over 60 years old, there were 5 (9%) people.

According to the classification of spleen injuries developed by the American Association of Surgeons-Traumatologists (AAST), splenic injuries have 5 degrees. As a result of a number of examinations, 8 (14.5%) patients were diagnosed with grade I, 26 (47%) – grade II, 11 (20%) III degree and 10 (18%) – IV degree. The victims were admitted to the emergency or intensive care unit, only 6 (10.9%) of them were transferred from other departments, and each of them underwent standard examinations (ultrasound of the abdominal cavity, general blood and urine tests, plain radiography of the abdominal cavity) to clarify the nature of the injury. All of them had clinical signs of anemia of varying degrees, and only 28 (50.9%) patients indicated pain in the left hypochondrium. Given the impossibility of accurately determining the degree of spleen damage, 14 (25.5%) patients had to undergo diagnostic laparoscopy. However, in other cases, MSCT and one of the modern and affordable methods – ultrasound – were used for diagnosis.

Results. Considering the I - II degree of damage, 32 (58%) patients were treated conservatively. Despite efforts to direct the operations to preserve the integrity of the spleen, based on the degree of damage and the viability of the organ, 13 (23.6%) patients had to undergo splenectomy . In addition, in 6

(10.9%) cases, general complications were observed as a result of treatment, and in 7 (12.7%) - surgical complications, such as suture divergence, wound infection, etc. Only in one case was it necessary to perform a repeat operation. Of the total, 3 (5.5%) cases were fatal.

Conclusions: Thus, Experience shows that the leading methods for diagnosing spleen damage in victims with splenic trauma are ultrasound and MSCT. Important prognostic factors for spleen trauma are an increase in the size of the organ and hematomas, especially if they are located in the central parts of the organ. Dynamic ultrasound for focal changes in the spleen allows for conservative management of patients. In turn, MSCT allows for a more precise character of traumatic changes in the spleen, the localization of focal lesions, and the structure and volume of inclusions in the parenchyma.

